

PARTICLE DYNAMICS AROUND THE MODMAX BLACK HOLE

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Abstract: In this paper, we investigate the particle dynamics around the ModMax black hole by using the Lagrangian formalism. We derive the equation for the effective potential of the neutral particle, and explore the effect of the spacetime parameters on it. Moreover, we study the MBOs and ISCOs of the massive particles around the ModMax black hole.

Here, we present an overview of the ModMax black hole spacetime and its associated geodesic dynamics. The spacetime geometry is described by the line element [1]:

$$ds^2 = -f(r)dt^2 + \frac{1}{f(r)}dr^2 + r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2), \tag{1}$$

where the metric function takes the form:

$$f(r) = 1 - \frac{2M}{r} + \frac{Q^2}{r^2}e^{-\gamma} \tag{2}$$

Here, Q represents the electric charge and γ denotes the screening parameter. Notably, the Reissner-Nordström solution is recovered when $\gamma=0$, while setting both $Q=0$ and $\gamma=0$ yields the Schwarzschild metric. Figure 1

FIG. 1: The left panel shows the radial dependence of the metric function $f(r)$ for different values of the BH charge. The screening parameter is fixed as $\gamma=-0.5$. The right panel illustrates the radial dependence of the metric function $f(r)$ for different values of the screening parameter γ . The BH charge is fixed as $Q=0.5$.

displays the radial behavior of $f(r)$ for various combinations of Q and γ . The event horizon locations, determined by $f(r)=0$, exhibit dependence on these parameters. The dynamics of test particles in this spacetime are governed by the Lagrangian [2]:

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2}mg_{\mu\nu}\frac{dx^\mu}{d\tau}\frac{dx^\nu}{d\tau}, \tag{3}$$

where τ is proper time and m is the particle mass. Setting $m=1$ for simplicity, the generalized momenta are:

$$p_\mu = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{x}^\mu} = g_{\mu\nu} \dot{x}^\nu. \tag{4}$$

For equatorial motion ($\theta = \pi/2$), the equations of motion become:

$$\begin{aligned} p_t &= -f(r)\dot{t} = -E, \\ p_\phi &= r^2\dot{\phi} = L, \\ p_r &= \frac{\dot{r}}{f(r)}, \\ p_\theta &= r^2\dot{\theta}, \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

FIG. 2: The plot shows the radial dependence of the effective potential for the different values of the spacetime parameters and the orbital angular momentum.

FIG. 3: The plot illustrates the dependence of the MBO parameters on the BH charge Q for different values of the γ parameters.

with E and L representing the conserved energy and angular momentum, respectively. The normalization condition leads to:

$$\dot{r}^2 + V_{\text{eff}} = E^2, \tag{6}$$

where the effective potential is given by [3]:

$$V_{\text{eff}} = f(r) \left(1 + \frac{L^2}{r^2} \right). \quad (7)$$

Figure 2 shows how V_{eff} varies with radius for different parameter values. The effective potential exhibits three key features: (1) it increases with black hole charge Q , (2) decreases with screening parameter γ , and (3) grows with particle angular momentum L .

Our analysis focuses on periodic orbits, which require specific energy and angular momentum conditions:

$$L_{\text{ISCO}} \leq L \text{ and } E_{\text{ISCO}} \leq E \leq E_{\text{MBO}} = 1. \quad (8)$$

FIG. 4: The plot demonstrates the dependence of the ISCO parameters on the BH charge Q for different values of the γ parameters.

The marginally bound orbit (MBO) is determined by [4]:

$$V_{\text{eff}} = 1 \text{ and } \frac{dV_{\text{eff}}}{dr} = 0, \quad (9)$$

while the innermost stable circular orbit (ISCO) satisfies:

$$\dot{r} = 0, \frac{dV_{\text{eff}}}{dr} = 0, \frac{d^2V_{\text{eff}}}{dr^2} = 0. \quad (10)$$

Figures 3 and 4 present numerical results for MBO and ISCO parameters. Both orbits show decreasing radial positions with increasing charge Q , but increasing values with larger screening parameter γ . These trends are consistent across all ISCO parameters (radius, angular momentum, and energy).

References

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